

**A STAKEHOLDER-ORIENTED STRATEGY FOR ENHANCING THE INVESTMENT
ATTRACTIVENESS OF CONSTRUCTION COMPANIES: DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPMENT
AND IMPLEMENTATION**

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Abstract

It has been demonstrated that the investment attractiveness of construction companies underpins the formulation and implementation of modern development strategies. It serves as an indicator of the capabilities and dynamism of construction companies, as well as the level of interaction with domestic and international investors.

Stakeholders influence the processes of ensuring investment attractiveness. They are characterised as groups of interested parties interacting within the system of production and economic activities of construction enterprises and are characterised by the influence of socio-economic, financial, investment, urban planning, spatial, environmental and security factors, the actions of which are aimed at shaping and implementing the development directions of companies, ensuring their investment attractiveness.

It has been established that a pressing issue is the identification of directions for the development and implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy for shaping the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

The development and implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy for building the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises involves the following stages: establishing an information and analytical system to support a stakeholder-oriented strategy for building investment attractiveness; the development and implementation of a theoretical and methodological approach to assessing the level of investment attractiveness of construction enterprises; the implementation of economic and mathematical modelling of factors influencing the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises; forecasting changes in the integrated indicator of the level of investment attractiveness of construction enterprises; identifying growth sectors; characterisation and assessment of the extent to which the external and internal environment influences the implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy for building investment attractiveness; development of a roadmap for implementing the stakeholder-oriented strategy; creation of scenarios for building the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises; development and implementation of scientifically grounded recommendations for increasing the level of investment attractiveness of construction enterprises, taking into account the influence of stakeholders; establishment of an organisational and economic mechanism for building the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

Keywords: investment attractiveness, construction companies, stakeholder-oriented strategy, scenarios.

Introduction. The investment attractiveness (IA) of construction enterprises (CE) underpins the formulation and implementation of their current development strategies. It serves as an indicator of the capabilities and activity of construction enterprises, as well as the level of interaction with domestic and international investors.

The investment attractiveness of construction enterprises is characterised as an integrated indicator determined by financial, economic, environmental and urban planning factors, the interaction between which is viewed through the prism of investment activity and the relationships between foreign and domestic investors,

developers, clients of construction products, design organisations, and other stakeholders to enhance the effectiveness of investment activities.

Stakeholders influence the processes of ensuring investment attractiveness. They are characterised as groups of interested parties interacting within the system of production and economic activities of construction enterprises and are characterised by the influence of socio-economic, financial, investment, urban planning, spatial, environmental and security factors, the effects of which are aimed at shaping and implementing the development directions of companies, ensuring their investment attractiveness.

In the current extraordinary conditions, influenced by the consequences of aggressive military operations,

a pressing issue is the development and implementation of a strategy as a comprehensive category that creates conditions for the development of construction enterprises.

A stakeholder-oriented strategy for building the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises is based on a theoretical, methodological and regulatory framework and is defined by a system of interrelated actions characterised by the influence of socio-economic, spatial, urban planning, security, investment, environmental and stakeholder factors, aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of investment attractiveness formation to ensure the development of construction enterprises.

At the same time, the question of identifying the key areas for the development and implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy to enhance the investment attractiveness of construction companies remains a pressing issue.

Justification of existing theoretical approaches.

It has been established that the consequences of Russian aggression influence the operations of construction companies, as well as the development and implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy for enhancing investment attractiveness. This necessitates a rethinking of approaches to the implementation of this strategy and ensuring effective stakeholder engagement. Furthermore, the processes described are exacerbated by the transformational processes taking place in the construction sector. In particular, the following areas are decisive: technical support for construction and the complexity of its implementation; the long-term nature of construction production; organisational features of the operation of construction enterprises; the definition and directions for building the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises; and managerial aspects of stakeholder interaction. In this context, the following developments should be noted [1, 2].

In the current climate, the following measures are proposed to ensure the stable operation of construction companies: improving safety standards; resuming operations of construction companies by ensuring a reliable supply of electricity and building materials; introducing and implementing housing reconstruction programmes at national and regional levels; and ensuring transparency in the implementation of the country's reconstruction programmes [3].

It should be noted that stakeholders influence the development and maintenance of investment attractiveness. They are defined as individuals or groups of individuals with an interest in any decisions or activities relating to the implementation of a project [4]. In line with the principles of this approach, stakeholders are defined as individuals, groups or organisations that may influence, be influenced by, or perceive themselves as being affected by a decision, action or outcome of the project [5].

The following key stakeholder groups have been identified: consumers and customers; suppliers; local authorities; tax and other regulatory bodies; shareholders, investors and owners; the community and civil society organisations; employees and their representative bodies; the media; credit rating agencies; financial institutions; and government bodies [6].

Applying a functional approach, the procedural aspects of stakeholder analysis are outlined as follows:

- preparatory stage (selection of experts for stakeholder analysis; selection of stakeholder analysis tools; development of the scale to be used during the analysis);

- analytical stage (identification and grouping of stakeholders (Stakeholder's Map); prioritisation of stakeholder groups based on the strength of their influence on the enterprise's activities using an analytical method; construction of a stakeholder group interests matrix based on a semantic analysis of the 'interests–threats' chain; identification of stakeholders using the 'power/interest' matrix; prioritisation of stakeholder groups' interests; construction of an interest balance matrix and calculation of the overall level of interest balance);

- strategic and managerial stage (identification of possible strategies for each stakeholder group; selection of an interaction strategy);

- monitoring stage (monitoring changes in stakeholders; monitoring changes in stakeholders' interests and influence; monitoring changes in the priorities of stakeholder groups; monitoring the interaction strategy) [6–8].

The proposed areas for developing a stakeholder-oriented approach to ensuring the development of construction companies:

- establishing an information and analytical framework regarding the interaction between stakeholders of construction companies and factors influencing their development;

- identification of stakeholder factors influencing the development of construction enterprises;

- development of a multi-level system of indicators;

- assessment of local stakeholder indicators using analytical and expert methods;

- developing models for assessing summary stakeholder indicators;

- assessing summary stakeholder indicators for construction companies;

- developing an integrated model for assessing the stakeholder indicator of construction companies' development;

- assessing the integrated indicator;

- interpreting the results obtained [9].

At the same time, questions remain unresolved regarding the identification of directions for the development and implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy for enhancing the investment attractiveness of construction companies.

The aim of the study is to identify directions for the development and implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy for enhancing the investment attractiveness of construction companies.

Main section. The development and implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy for enhancing the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises involves the following stages:

1. Establishment of an information and analytical system to support a stakeholder-oriented strategy

for enhancing the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

2. Development and implementation of a theoretical and methodological approach to assessing the level of investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

3. Conducting economic and mathematical modelling of factors influencing the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

4. Forecasting changes in the integrated indicator of the level of investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

5. Identification of sectors for growth in the level of investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

6. Characterisation and assessment of the extent to which the external and internal environment influences the implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy for building the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

7. Development of a roadmap for the implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy.

8. Creation of scenarios for the development of investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

9. Development and implementation of scientifically grounded recommendations for increasing the level of investment attractiveness of construction enterprises, taking into account the influence of stakeholders.

10. Establishment of an organisational and economic mechanism for building the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

The development of an information and analytical system to support a stakeholder-oriented strategy for building the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises is based on the results of analytical and expert assessments of the relevant local factors.

The development and implementation of a theoretical and methodological approach to assessing the level of investment attractiveness of construction enterprises has made it possible to determine an integrated indicator and form an important element of the quantitative basis for creating a stakeholder-oriented strategy.

In developing the presented strategy, the results of economic and mathematical modelling of construction enterprises' investment attractiveness factors are applied as the second element of the quantitative basis.

Forecasting changes in the integrated indicator of the level of development of construction enterprises' investment attractiveness has made it possible to identify sectors of growth in the level of development of construction enterprises' investment attractiveness. This is the third element of the quantitative basis for a stakeholder-oriented strategy. The characterisation and assessment of the extent to which the external and internal environments influence the implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy for building the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises is carried out using SWOT analysis, the importance of which is emphasised in [10, 11].

As part of the development and implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy, the following scenarios for enhancing the investment attractiveness of construction companies have been proposed:

– **pessimistic**: characterised by a permanent decline in the index of investment attractiveness of construction enterprises, a reduction in the effectiveness of stakeholder interaction in the field of investment activity, a deepening of the slowdown in the development of construction enterprises, a decline in production capacity, the level of working capital utilisation, operational efficiency, liquidity, and the use of equity and debt capital; problematic issues accumulate in the security, environmental, investment and innovation sectors, as well as in overcoming the consequences of Russian aggression; and issues regarding ensuring the effective functioning of the construction sector remain unresolved. The level of provision and implementation of monitoring procedures declines. It should be noted that the index of investment attractiveness ranges from 0 to 4;

– **stabilisation**: characterised by mixed trends in the investment attractiveness index of construction enterprises, where periods of growth alternate with decline and vice versa; the level of stakeholder interaction in investment activities is stabilising, trends in the development of construction enterprises are evident, there is an unsystematic strengthening of production capacity, an increase in the utilisation of working capital, operational efficiency, liquidity provision, and the use of equity and borrowed capital; the security, environmental, investment and innovation situation is stabilising despite the impact of the Russian Federation's aggression; and there are isolated positive developments in the construction sector. Monitoring procedures are implemented in a non-systematic manner. The investment attractiveness index ranges from 4.01 to 6;

– **transitional**: non-systematic trends in the growth of the investment attractiveness index for construction enterprises are identified; the level of stakeholder interaction in the field of investment activity is increasing; trends in the development of construction enterprises in specific areas are observed; production capacity and working capital are being strengthened; profitability and liquidity are increasing; the level of utilisation of equity and borrowed capital is increasing; the scope for applying security, economic, investment and innovation instruments is being strengthened despite the impact of the Russian Federation's aggression; positive developments are taking place in the construction sector. A monitoring mechanism has been established for the formation and use of investment resources. The index of investment attractiveness formation ranges from 6.01 to 8;

– **development**: systemic trends in the growth of the investment attractiveness index for construction enterprises have been identified; the level of stakeholder interaction in the field of investment activity is increasing; trends in the development of business processes are observed; production capacity and working capital are being strengthened; profitability and liquidity are increasing; the level of utilisation of equity and borrowed capital is increasing; the application of security, economic, investment and innovation tools is consistently ensured despite the impact of the Russian Federation's

aggression; and the construction sector is developing. There is ongoing monitoring of the formation and use of investment resources. The investment attractiveness index ranges from 8.01 to 10.

Conclusions. Thus, the conceptual framework for defining a stakeholder-oriented strategy for enhancing the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises has been refined. This strategy is based on theoretical approaches that characterise the types and levels of interaction among stakeholders, the specific features of ensuring the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises, and includes a system of interrelated actions that takes into account the influence of socio-economic, spatial, urban planning, security, investment, environmental and stakeholder factors. This makes it possible to establish a strategic framework for increasing the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

Approaches to the development and application of strategic tools have been further refined; these are defined by the proposed roadmap and the results of the SWOT analysis, which provide the means to establish an informational and functional foundation for the creation and implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy for enhancing the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

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